

TECHNOLOGIES FOR MINING AND PROCESSING OF RARE EARTH ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT. Rare earth elements are critically needed to produce high-tech products, such as electric cars, electronic equipment, renewable energy technologies, and means for the defence industry. However, their extraction and processing pose a serious challenge due to the complexity of the process itself, the high associated production costs, the difficult integration of new and cutting-edge technologies into the processes, the growing geopolitical risks, as well as local environmental protection laws. Optimising the extraction and processing processes of rare earth elements will help to guarantee and secure supply chains, which are essential for the continuity of the production process. The introduction of modern and advanced technologies has the potential to optimise costs, increase the efficiency of work processes, minimise the negative impact on the environment, and thus ensure the sustainability of mining. On a global scale, rare earth elements will become increasingly valuable, which implies serious investments by businesses in the development and implementation of new technologies in mining activities to ensure the sustainability of the industry itself.

Key words: technologies, mining, processing, rare earth elements (REEs).

ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ЗА ДОБИВ И ПРЕРАБОТКА НА РЕДКОЗЕМНИ ЕЛЕМЕНТИ

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РЕЗЮМЕ. Редкоземните елементи са критично необходими за производството на високотехнологични продукти като електрически автомобили, електронно оборудване, технологии за възобновяема енергия и средства за отбранителната промишленост. Въпреки това техният добив и обработка представляват сериозно предизвикателство поради сложността на самия процес, високите свързани производствени разходи, трудното интегриране на нови и авангардни технологии в процесите, нарастващите геополитически рискове, както и местните закони за опазване на околната среда. Оптимизирането на процесите на добив и обработка на редкоземни елементи ще помогне за гарантиране и осигуряване на веригите за доставки, които са от съществено значение за непрекъснатостта на производствения процес. Въвеждането на съвременни и напреднали технологии има потенциал да оптимизира разходите, да повиши ефективността на работните процеси, да сведе до минимум отрицателното въздействие върху околната среда и по този начин да гарантира устойчивостта на минното дело. В световен мащаб редкоземните елементи ще стават все по-ценни, което предполага сериозни инвестиции от страна на бизнеса в разработването и внедряването на нови технологии в минните дейности, за да се гарантира устойчивостта на самата индустрия.

Ключови думи: технологии, добив, преработка, редкоземни елементи

Introduction

In the third decade of the 21st century, all industries, including mining, are facing serious economic, social, environmental, and climate challenges, which implies a transformation of conventional production processes based on innovation and integration of modern new technologies into the activity. In the face of the need for transformation, a rethink of long-term priorities is needed, and the introduction of innovation in industry would have an impact on increasing the flexibility and sustainability of activities and markets (Galabova, 2022). The mining industry has been and continues to be a key factor in the economy of each country, and today a successful energy transition is of particular importance, which should ensure the availability of critical mineral raw materials, among which rare earth elements constitute a significant part. The strategy of every mining company should include the integration of the basic principles of sustainable development, which includes a balanced combination of economic efficiency, social responsibility and environmental sustainability. Companies in the mineral and raw materials sector today have an increasingly important role in the sustainability of society. The lessons of the crisis that we must follow are that society requires much greater commitment and cohesion, as well as responsibility (Trifonova, B., 2022). In this regard, the application of new innovative technologies in the activity can lead to the optimisation of the consumption of natural resources, more effective management of energy and raw material flows, and a reduction in the carbon

footprint of a given enterprise, thus ensuring the sustainability of production processes.

The mining industry, being a significant contributor to the challenges, related to escalating threats of irreversible climate change, biodiversity loss, inequality, poverty, and social conflicts, is actively undergoing a transformative process to align itself with the principles of innovation and sustainability. As Tomova & Kisiov (2023) stated, mining industries are the very first link of a long supply chain. The raw materials are feedstock materials for many industries and mining industry significantly contributes to technological development as such.

This article thoroughly examines the approaches being developed by the mining industry, encompassing the adoption of new technologies and enhanced social approaches aimed at improving its often-unfavourable public perception. According to Correia et al. (2024), “the widespread adoption of novel practices and technologies by the mining industry is a pivotal enabler of the energy transition, ensuring the availability of critical mineral raw materials while promoting sustainability.”

It is in this context that rare earth elements play a key role, as they are critical raw materials for both the production of high-tech products and for technological development in general. Entire strategic industries in the relevant countries depend on rare earth elements as an indispensable component of high-tech production processes. This includes the production of electric vehicles, devices powered by renewable energy sources, telecommunications equipment, battery power systems, medical machinery, defence technologies, and others.

The growing demand and key importance of rare earth elements for the transformation of industries in global economies requires that they be examined in more detail from the perspective of the implementation and use of new innovative technologies for their mining and processing.

Materials and methods

This study aims to conduct a systematic literature analysis of the currently existing modern technologies for the extraction and processing of rare earth elements, with the focus on the theoretical aspects and the summary of scientific and technical achievements in the field of mining.

This theoretical study used various materials such as scientific articles and technical reports, industry publications and reports, as well as official documents on technical, legislative, and environmental topics. The results achieved from field studies of the activities of mining, processing, and recycling of rare earth elements were of particular interest. Valuable practical information is also provided by materials from the business, related to efficiency, operating costs, integration of new technologies in the activity, and the impact on the environment because of their use. Regulatory documents, as well as the relevant standards for mining and processing of rare earth elements, were also considered.

The materials used in this study were selected based on criteria related to proximity to the topic of the study, the relevance of the data, the diverse geographical distribution in different regions of the world, the diversity of perspectives, and finally – the peer-reviewed nature of the publications.

The analysis focuses on the theoretical aspects and the generalisation of technological achievements in the field of mining, considering their scientific and technical characteristics. For this purpose, the following research methods have been applied: a comprehensive systematic search in authoritative scientific databases for relevant keywords such as "mining", "rare earth elements", "processing", "bioleaching", "sustainability", etc.; extraction of key information from the selected literature, followed by synthesis and analysis of the data to identify relevant trends, patterns, conclusions, and recommendations; comparative analysis of key parameters of the different technologies and methods for mining and processing of rare earth elements; critical assessment based on their viability, efficiency, and technological maturity.

Overview of rare earth elements

Rare earth elements (REEs) are part of the group of strategic raw materials and constitute a group of 17 chemically similar metallic elements that are widely used in the creation of high technology and modern industry. Although their name suggests that they are rather rare and difficult to find, these elements are relatively abundant in the Earth's crust, with their average concentration being approximately 169.1 parts per million (ppm). It is important to note that their economic viability is greatly influenced by their geographical concentration, as well as by the mineralogical form in which they occur.

Rare earth element deposits are unevenly distributed worldwide, with the world's richest countries in these natural resources being China, followed by Vietnam, Brazil, Russia, Australia, the United States, Greenland, Tanzania, Canada, and South Africa. China, Vietnam, Russia, and Brazil together hold

86.9% of the world's reserves (Shuai et al., 2024). At the same time, the leading position in world markets is once again taken by the "People's Republic of China", with the "Celestial Empire" producing between 70% and 90% of the total world supply of rare earth elements.

Figure 1. Global distribution of rare earth element production in 2024 (percentage share).

Source: Authors' compilation based on data from Statista.com.

As illustrated in Figure 1, China accounted for nearly 70% of global rare earth element production in 2024, followed by the United States (11.6%) and Myanmar (7.97%). The remaining production is distributed among smaller producers, such as Australia, Thailand, Nigeria, and others. This concentration of supply poses a critical geopolitical risk and highlights the fragility of global value chains in the REE sector.

This fact has largely been one of the main reasons for the geopolitical conflict between the USA and China this year, and in this regard, Canada and the EU have also taken measures to diversify supply chains and at least partially ensure their own domestic production (Chen et al., 2024). The reserves of rare earth elements worldwide amount to approximately 130 million tonnes. Of the total resource, the largest share of approximately one third falls on China – about 44 million tonnes. At the same time, the Chinese are leaders in the exploration and production of rare earth elements. In turn, the United States was the leading country in this market until 1998, when, for economic and environmental reasons, they stopped mining (Balaram, 2019).

Rare earth elements are extremely valuable for world economies, as they are indispensable and applicable in many different fields, such as electronics, optics, aerospace, biomedicine, energy chemistry or catalysis, and energy-related technologies. This wide applicability is largely due to the unique properties of rare earth elements – magnetism, luminescence, and electromechanics. From the point of view of importance as commercial resources, the main minerals containing rare earth elements are bastnaesite, monazite and xenotime. They are sources of valuable light rare elements for modern high-tech industries, which are used to produce powerful magnets, catalysts, and some electronic components, while xenotime contains a large number of rare elements, which are used mainly in the development of optical systems and in the development of some nuclear technologies. Deposits associated with carbonatites, a type of igneous rock, are of economic and strategic importance due to their high content of rare earth elements. To use rare earth elements in a sustainable and economically efficient way as a basic resource for the development of modern and advanced technologies, it is

important to understand their mineralogical and geological characteristics (Chen et al., 2024).

This year, and in the recent past, rare earth supply chains have particularly been threatened by increasing geopolitical risks. At the same time, however, global supply chains are vulnerable due to the complex nature of rare earth mining and processing, related to geological specificity, technological labour intensity of mining and processing, limited technological capacities, as well as economic and regulatory uncertainty in the sector. At the same time, global demand is escalating, which requires finding more efficient mining methods, which are often associated with the integration of new and reliable technologies. To date, research efforts are focused on geologically discovering new rare earth deposits, improving the efficiency of their recycling, and, possibly, identifying substitutes, through which to minimise the risks associated with global supplies and the negative impact of their use on the environment. In this way, the aim is to ensure the long-term stability of industries, especially the ones directly dependent on these critical raw materials to produce goods.

Sustainable extraction technologies

The global demand for electric vehicles, renewable energy, and advanced technologies are driving the extraction and processing of rare earth elements. However, traditional methods inflict substantial environmental damage, including soil pollution, generation of radioactive waste, and overconsumption of water. According to Tomova (2023), many efforts have been made in the past few decades by the extractive industries to prevent, reduce, and minimise, as far as possible, the negative impacts because of the management of extractive waste and the extraction activities. To reduce the impact of these mining technologies, unsustainable extraction technologies and waste management methods are optimised through industrial innovation. This set of approaches aims to improve environmental outcomes through waste reduction, cleaner extraction processes, and circular economy practices. The case of rare earth elements will frame this discourse on the paradigm shift for the development, implementation, and prospective advanced sustainable technologies for extraction and processing aimed at reengineering systematic approaches classification.

Advances in bioleaching

Bioleaching has emerged as a practical and eco-friendly method for recovering metal from electronic waste, or "e-waste," to address resource depletion and environmental concerns. Unlike conventional pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical processes, bioleaching uses microorganisms to produce organic or inorganic acids and cyanides, facilitating metal solubilisation through processes such as acidolysis, redoxolysis, and complexolysis. Because it is cost-effective, energy-efficient, and operates in a temperate climate, this technique is a good alternative to urban mining (Baniasadi et al., 2019).

By encouraging metal solubilisation, bioleaching uses microorganisms to extract rare earth elements (REEs) from ores or industrial waste. *Pseudomonas putida* and *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* are two examples of acidophilic bacteria that have shown promise in leaching rare earth elements (REEs) from monazite and bastnaesite ores (Brierley and Kuhn, 2010; Macaskie et al., 2017; Mowafy, 2020). Bioleaching uses microorganisms in a process that includes the usage of

chemolithoautotrophs like *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans*, fungi such as *Aspergillus niger*, and cyanogenic bacteria like *Chromobacterium violaceum*. From copper, nickel, cobalt, and gold, these organisms bioleach metals from e-waste, like spent batteries and printed circuit boards (PCBs). These organisms are especially helpful in the recovery of gold because they can produce cyanide, which forms stable complexes with gold (Baniasadi et al., 2019). Copper can also be bioleached from the waste obtained from ground circuit boards with very high efficiency. In many of the experiments carried out, the yield obtained is over 90% (Toshev, 2022). Catalytic bioleaching, which uses catalysts like metal ions (like Cu^{2+} and Ag^{2+}) and carbon-based materials (like graphene and biochar) to improve reaction kinetics and metal recovery rates, is one example of bioleaching advancements. To maximise microbial performance and resistance to the toxic nature of e-waste, genetic engineering and omics techniques are also being investigated. For instance, it has been shown that modified strains of *C. violaceum* produce more cyanide and recover gold better (Tay et al., 2013).

According to C. L. Brierley (2010), "Bioleaching lends itself economically and technically to the processing of small deposits that cannot support high capital costs, remote deposits where making and shipping concentrates may not be a viable option, low-grade ores that cannot be cost-effectively treated by existing technologies, and complex ores. Bioleaching also offers opportunities as an auxiliary process for on-site generation of acid for adjunct operations, such as base metal oxide heap leaching."

Bioleaching has many benefits over traditional acid-based leaching, such as a smaller environmental impact, less energy consumption, and less chemical use. The selectivity of the process is limited by the similar chemical behavior of REEs, which presents a technical challenge, and the kinetics of microbial processes are frequently slower. Despite its benefits, bioleaching has drawbacks, including sluggish dissolution kinetics, e-waste's toxicity to microbes, and precipitation problems like jarosite formation. For bioleaching to be scaled up to industrial levels, these constraints must be addressed by microbial adaptation, catalyst application, and process optimisation (Baniasadi et al., 2019).

Genetic engineering, synthetic biology, and bioreactor configuration are three advanced approaches to improving the efficiency and stability of microbial populations. Merging bioleaching with traditional methods promises to improve the yields of recovery while reducing the environmental footprint, thereby guaranteeing the sustainable recovery of base metals. Additional research will be required to address the scalability of such technologies to industrial processes to ensure cost-effectiveness, as well as regulatory compliance to prepare for large-scale use.

Bioleaching's potential for sustainable metal recovery from e-waste is still being studied, with an emphasis on enhancing its environmental impact, scalability, and efficiency. Baniasadi et al. (2019) assert that "bioleaching is a sustainable method for metal recovery from e-waste and development of urban mining, which can help to save the non-renewable energy consumed in mining industry and provide mitigation of greenhouse gas emission." Bioleaching will become a more appealing alternative to conventional methods in the circular economy as future research attempts to increase metal recovery rates by refining microbial strains and process parameters.

Green Solvents: Ionic Liquids and Deep Eutectic Solvents

When it comes to REE extraction, green chemistry techniques – specifically, the use of ionic liquids (ILs) and deep eutectic solvents (DESs) – have shown a lot of promise in replacing traditional organic solvents. Recyclability, chemical tunability, and low volatility are characteristics of these solvents. A practical option for selective REE recovery from complex matrices is provided by DESs which are both economical and biodegradable (Charton et al., 2024). Recent research has shown that ILs and DESs can successfully extract neodymium, dysprosium, and europium with high separation factors at moderate temperatures and pH levels that are close to neutral (Ayora et al., 2019). The mild nature of these solvents in processing is at the heart of their environmental advantages, reducing the need for strict pH control and the likelihood of producing hazardous byproducts. In addition, scientists can work to alter both the selectivity and metal loading properties, which would allow them to address practical extraction challenges by purposefully altering the chemical structures of the ionic liquids themselves (Pereira et al., 2022).

The composition of DESs is a major advantage; these solvents are made from affordable, biodegradable ingredients and can be customised to recover specific REEs from waste streams and complex secondary resources (Charton et al., 2024). According to recent research, the modular nature of DESs enables fine adjustment of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, enabling highly selective extraction systems while controlling operational costs (Ayora et al., 2019; Abbott et al., 2020). DESs are promising for widespread industrial use because of their flexibility, which improves the efficiency and purity that can be achieved.

However, there are still obstacles to real industrial integration. These obstacles are related to the toxicity of some ionic liquids and deep eutectic solvents, their long-term physical and chemical stability, and the lack of a clear understanding of their real life cycle sustainability (Pereira et al., 2022; Charton et al., 2024). However, green solvents are positioned as key for the future development of sustainable mining and recycling of strategic raw materials, which is largely due to the significant progress in the development of green chemistry, as well as the ever-increasing political pressure for responsible mining and production of rare earth elements.

Membrane Separation Technologies

Supported liquid membranes (SLMs) and nanofiltration (NF) are two membrane-based methods that are becoming more popular as substitutes for conventional solvent extraction procedures. With the use of these techniques, REEs can be transported selectively across membranes with little energy and chemical reagents. Although these systems are still in the early stages of development for widespread use, recent pilot projects have shown that they are feasible for treating industrial wastewater and recovering electronic waste from leachates (Elbasher et al., 2021; Ren et al., 2021). Specifically, thin-film nanocomposite membranes and hollow fiber-supported SLMs have shown excellent permeability and selectivity, enabling targeted separation of REEs even in challenging aqueous conditions. According to recent reviews, the environmental impact of REE recovery processes, as well as waste volumes, can be decreased by incorporating membrane technologies into circular economy frameworks (Kaczorowska, 2023). These cutting-edge technologies provide a scalable and modular solution that can be tailored to different industrial applications

and waste streams. Membrane-based separation is anticipated to be essential to the long-term recovery of vital raw materials with further development.

Sustainable Recycling of REEs

Urban mining, or the extraction of rare earth elements from electronic waste, or "e-waste," is a crucial component of a sustainable REE supply chain. Electric car motors, permanent magnets in hard drives, and phosphors in fluorescent lights are examples of rich secondary sources. In hydrometallurgical processes, acid leaching is usually followed by solvent extraction or precipitation. *Hitachi* and *Umicore* have developed industrial-scale techniques for recovering rare earth elements from magnets, significantly reducing environmental impacts compared to primary mining (Tanaka et al., 2013). Furthermore, although they are usually only employed at the pilot or lab scale, electrochemical methods for recovering rare earth elements from solutions are growing in popularity because of their potential for high purity and low energy consumption (Kim et al., 2021).

Rare earth elements can now be extracted more efficiently from e-waste without dissolving excessive impurities, thanks to the development of electrochemical separation and selective leaching. In this regard, the combination of biosorption and bioelectrochemical systems is a low-energy solution that works effectively for the treatment of dilute or complex waste (Brown et al., 2023). Combining bioleaching and electrowinning methods can improve recovery rates, while reducing the need for additional chemicals and waste. Furthermore, the use of ionic liquid-based solvents shows both excellent selectivity and reusability. The latter makes it a significantly more environmentally friendly method for the extraction of rare earth elements from urban mine streams (Botelho Junior et al., 2023). These new ideas point to a move toward greener and more circular ways to recover important critical materials. As tech keeps getting better, urban mining is set to play a key role in managing resources sustainably in the rare earth sector.

Substitution Technologies for Rare Earth Elements

The creation of functional substitutes has become a supplementary tactic to extraction and recycling in light of the ongoing difficulties in obtaining rare earth elements in a sustainable manner. The goal of substitution technologies is to substitute more plentiful, less hazardous, and more commercially feasible materials for rare earth elements in vital applications, especially in magnets, phosphors, and catalysts.

Magnet Substitution. A significant amount of the world's consumption of rare earth elements comes from permanent magnets, particularly neodymium–iron–boron (NdFeB) magnets. They are crucial components of consumer electronics, wind turbines, and electric motors due to their remarkable magnetic performance. However, with varying degrees of success, researchers have looked into alternatives.

Manganese–aluminum (Mn–Al) alloys and iron–nitride compounds (such as Fe_{16}N_2) have demonstrated potential as rare-earth-free magnetic materials. Although these systems are more prevalent and safer for the environment, they usually have a lower magnetic energy product than NdFeB (Coey, 2012). Because cobalt is a crucial component in and of itself, cobalt–iron alloys are limited by high material costs and supply chain risks, despite their effectiveness. The creation of nanostructured composite magnets, which combine soft and hard magnetic phases to replicate the behavior of REE-based magnets, is one

noteworthy development (Skomski & Coey, 2016). New developments in exchange-spring magnets have demonstrated encouraging outcomes in terms of increasing coercivity and decreasing dependence on rare earth elements. Furthermore, the tuneable magnetic properties and potential for competitive performance without critical materials of high-entropy alloys are being investigated.

Phosphor Substitution in Lighting and Displays. Fluorescent lights and display technologies frequently use rare earth phosphors, like terbium and europium. Alternatively, semiconductor nanoparticles with tuneable luminescence, known as quantum dots (QDs), have drawn interest due to their high efficiency and colour purity. Quantum dots derived from carbon-based nanomaterials or indium phosphide are good alternatives devoid of hazardous heavy metals and rare earth elements (Song et al., 2015). However, because of their toxicity, cadmium-based QDs are still being closely monitored by regulators.

A rare-earth-free alternative is provided by organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs), particularly for display applications. OLED technology completely removes the need for REE-based phosphors, but it is still very expensive.

Catalyst Substitution. Cerium and lanthanum are frequently used in petroleum cracking and automotive catalysts. Alternatives with advantageous and thermal stability characteristics have been researched, including spinel materials and perovskite-type oxides (such as LaMnO_3 and SrFeO_3). These substances lessen dependency on rare elements while providing similar catalytic performance (Royer et al., 2014). In certain industrial formulations, transition-metal oxides (such as manganese, cobalt, and nickel) are already utilised for partial substitution in three-way catalytic converters. Nonetheless, attaining comparable performance to rare-earth-based catalysts while reducing costs continues to be a significant obstacle for broader implementation.

Challenges and Future Outlook. Many high-performance applications still find it technically difficult to totally replace rare earth elements even with major developments. One of the key difficulties is matching the durability, thermal stability, and efficiency of REE-based materials. The need for new manufacturing infrastructure and material standardisation also often restricts industrial-scale adoption.

Figure 2 illustrates the global reserves of rare earth elements between 2010 and 2024. Global rare earths reserves peaked in 2013, when reserves amounted to 140 million metric tons. Despite increasing industrial demand, total reserves have shown only limited growth, with a notable decline in 2024 to 90 million metric tonnes. This trend underscores the urgency of diversifying sourcing strategies and investing in advanced technologies for resource recovery and substitution.

The research on hybrid solutions – such as functional layering of alternative materials or partial substitution – keeps growing, though. Ongoing creativity in material design and circular economy strategies could help the rare earth industry to move toward a more robust and environmentally responsible future. Innovative recycling combined with advances in alternative materials could one day allow a closed-loop system that reduces primary extraction.

Figure 2. Total global reserves of rare earth elements, 2010–2024 (in million metric tonnes).

Source: Compiled by the authors using data from Statista.com.

Conclusion

Rare earth elements (REEs) are in high demand worldwide because of their critical roles in the production of electric vehicles, defence systems, electronics, and clean energy technologies. However, the conventional REE supply chain is becoming less and less sustainable due to energy-intensive mining, environmental deterioration, and geopolitical dependencies. This study looked at three main approaches to deal with these issues: sustainable extraction, recycling, and substitution.

Secondary source recycling, especially e-waste, has already shown industrial viability, but infrastructure improvements for collection and sorting are still crucial. Despite present efficiency and scalability constraints, bioleaching and green solvents provide environmentally friendly substitutes for traditional extraction. Although substitution technologies are promising, particularly in the areas of magnets, phosphors, and catalysts, they still face performance and cost obstacles to wider use.

For a more environmentally friendly and circular economy-friendly extraction of rare earth raw materials, new technological methods are being developed in the field of membrane separation, ionic liquids, deep eutectic solvents, and genetically modified microbial processes. Of particular importance here is the so-called urban mining, which combines hydrometallurgical, electrochemical and biotechnological techniques, with the help of which high yields are ensured. At the same time, sustainable mining and recycling initiatives can be supported by the implementation of techniques for the substitution of rare earth elements. Although these measures have only a private application, they can still limit the huge demand.

Integrating these various strategies into unified, scalable, and internationally coordinated systems is essential to the future of REE supply. Aligning material flows with environmental and geopolitical sustainability will require investment in hybrid technologies (like partial substitution and modular recycling platforms), regulatory frameworks, and life-cycle analysis. For a truly green technological future, striking this balance is now a technical, financial, and environmental requirement rather than merely a theoretical objective.

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